

STUDY OF CENTRAL GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES TO IMPLEMENT NEP 2020 IN SCHOOL EDUCATION, HIGHER EDUCATION AND TEACHER EDUCATION TO ACHIEVE ITS OBJECTIVE

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Abstract

To reach one's greatest potential and create a just and equal society, high-quality education is essential. The benefit to society increases with the level of education among its members. In India, various education policies have been framed from time to time. This study aims to examine how the New National Education Policy 2020 is being implemented in Amritsar district's colleges and schools. By creating a questionnaire, the fundamental data were gathered for this purpose from different institutions and schools. A percentage analysis has been done and tables with the gathered data have been displayed. The study's findings indicated that the majority of college and school instructors supported NEP 2020 as they were of the opinion that it would prove beneficial for the economy, in general and schools and colleges in particular. But there are certain challenges related to the implementation of NEP 2020. There may be lack of cooperation from States as education is part of concurrent list so State government can oppose the implementation of NEP 2020. Non- Availability of skilled teachers for elementary education may create hindrance in the effective implementation of NEP 2020 etc. Thus, NEP 2020 may bring positive changes in the Indian Academic sector, if implemented efficiently and effectively.

Introduction

The goal of education is to accomplish a number of objectives, including the dissemination of knowledge and the skill enhancement and character qualities. The

development of one's emotional, social, physical, and spiritual components of life is the goal of education. Knowledge gained during infancy, childhood, adolescence, youth, and manhood is all included in education. It highlights how important education is in creating law-abiding citizens, encouraging social cohesiveness, and tackling societal problems. Every country's perception of education makes it clear that the environment there is important and that education has a significant role in addressing it (Verma and Kumar, 2021).

In India, various education policies have been framed from time to time. Everyone has a right for education and according to Indian Education Policies; it is free and compulsory for every child at least for the elementary and fundamental stages for schooling. The significance of universal literacy is that it is an instrument for mobilizing the people, arousing community consciousness and participation for bringing social change. (Pandit, 2016). The government led by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi announced the first National Policy on Education in 1968, based on the findings and recommendations of the Kothari Commission (1964–1966). The policy advocated equal educational opportunities and a "radical restructuring" in order to achieve national integration. In order to establish a thorough framework for the advancement of education throughout the nation, the Rajiv Gandhi administration unveiled education policy in 1986. This strategy intended for equalizing educational opportunities and removing disadvantages, with a focus on scheduled castes, scheduled tribes, and Indian women in particular. The NPE 1986 had a significant influence on the Indian educational system and acted as a roadmap for further educational advancements. In 1992, it underwent revisions to accommodate evolving educational demands and obstacles.

National Education Policy 2020:

2020 has been a year of reconstruction and upheavals. Our outlook on policy has undergone enormous alterations as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak. After a 36-year hiatus, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 was finally announced on July 29, 2020, to a mixture of interest, excitement, and a good dose of skepticism and criticism. The global crises of COVID- 19 virus and subsequent lockdowns imposed by the government to control the situation has forced the people to stay indoors which impacted the education sector tremendously. (Chakraborty, 2020).

“National Education Policy 2020 envisions an India-centric education system that contributes directly to transforming our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society by providing high-quality education to all.” India has the second-biggest educational system globally, after China. As a result, formulating policies for the biggest

democracy in the world involves extensive discussion. Because it is the first comprehensive educational policy since India's liberalization in 1991 and the subsequent economic reforms that signaled a shift from a centralised economic planning model to an opening of markets to globalisation, the policy addresses the needs of an entirely different economy than the one in 1986. The Ministry of Human Resources Development will now be known as the Ministry of Education, which is the biggest change included in the NEP 2020. By taking this action, the policy changes the emphasis and clarifies that citizens are not just human capital. The aim of the NEP 2020 is to sustain and take care of the existing vibrant knowledge society, by providing high-quality education to all, without having discrimination of caste, religion, gender. (kumar, 2020).

Goal 4 (SDG4) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which India adopted in 2015, is a reflection of the global education development agenda. It aims to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all" by 2030. The entire educational system needs to be changed to support and encourage learning in order to reach all of the main aims and goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs) and achieve such a high standard. The national education policy (NEP 2020), unveiled by the union cabinet on July 29, 2020, lays out the objectives of India's future educational system. The current national education strategy replaces the one from 1986. The strategy provides a thorough framework for both vocational training and elementary education in India's rural and urban areas. By 2030, the strategy seeks to completely overhaul India's educational system. Parents, educators, and many other individuals who are either directly or indirectly involved in the school system recommended this regulation (kalyani, 2020).

In order to bring school education more in step with worldwide trends, the NEP undertakes certain radical policy reforms, such as switching from a content-based education to a pedagogical approach. The intention is to coincide with educational research by offering recommendations for a language policy while allowing governments to make the final decisions about how to implement it. However, language issues have always been contentious. This is not an anomaly. The policy presents a number of recommendations for primary education with a focus on early childhood foundational reading and language development. Strong teacher education is emphasized as a means of achieving this goal. The aim of education in schools is to begin with activity-based learning and gradually transition to critical and transdisciplinary learning, making a dramatic break from the streams of science, business, and the arts. Based on this policy, the Indian education system is moving from teacher centric to

learner centric, particular to all round development, marks centric to skill centric, Information centric to knowledge centric, examination centric to experimental centric. (Sarkar and Sarkar 2020). Unprecedented latitude in developing multidisciplinary curricula, an academic credential system, and numerous exit options to accommodate individual ambitions has been granted to the higher education sector. The revisions in the Higher Education policy are framed by a general focus on research and technology, as well as 3- and 4-year degrees, 1- and 2-year master's programs, and more. The creation of a National Research Foundation, which would finance and coordinate research projects from various government agencies, academic institutions, and commercial and charitable groups, could help the higher education sector produce creative, peer-reviewed research. Although NEP2020 makes it easier for foreign colleges to enroll in the nation, laws surrounding this still need to be clarified.

Implementation of NEP 2020 requires various initiatives and actions, taken by various educational bodies in a systematic manner, e.x Union and States government, Ministry of Education, NTA, UGC etc. UGC has set up five zonal committees to facilitate universities in the effective implementation of NEP 2020. The five committees cover the northern, northern eastern, eastern, western, southern and central regions. Initiatives like the Academic Bank of Credit regulation, which promotes flexibility and facilitates student mobility; the guidelines for multiple entry and exit in academic programs; online education to increase access and GER; the regulations on the credit framework for online courses through Swayam 2021 for recognition and integration of credits; the regulation to facilitate vocational education to enhance employability; the emphasis on research and innovation; value added courses for undergraduates, etc., are just a few of the initiatives on which UGC has focused.

Review of Literature

Kaurav *et.al.*, (2020) conducted the qualitative analysis of NEP (2020). According to them, NEP (2020) not only focuses on the development of the community stakeholders and the education system but it also revamps the current assessment criteria. Kour (2022) analyzed the NEP (2020) and language learning in India. She conducted the critical assessment of National Education policy 2020. She states that National education policy of India 2020 outlines the country's plan for the new century. Its goals to give every body the access to a decent education, which aligns with SDG4 of agenda 2030.

Malik (2020) described NEP (2020) and it comparative analysis with RTE. He claims that although there are many pulses in this policy, it still has to be enhanced. NEP (2020) has the potential to become the greatest policy in the fields of education and human resources if it

continues to make policy revisions. Manivaskan (2021) described the viewpoint on NEP 2020 with respect to higher education fragmented higher education system with majority of institutions that concentrate only on one disciplined more institutions are running with a smaller number of students. Reddy (2020) analyzed the challenges and opportunities of NEP (2020). In his view, the strategy necessitates rapid cooperation between federal and state authorities in order to create newly suggested bodies, specify guidelines for schools, and create convergence of different programs and acts with NEP (2020). Rani (2022) conducted the issues and challenges of national educational policy 2020. He describes that the concern for improvement of education has been at the top of India's development. The new education policy seeks to positively upgrades the present education system. It is bundled with some very innovative and contemporary proposals. NEP (2020) was critically examined by Venkateshwarlu (2020), who also talked about its problems, strategies, and difficulties. He said that this strategy, which glosses over our primary goal of access to education—which has long prevailed—is a vision statement that fails to be inclusive of the lowest strata of society and offers little to no assistance to the impoverished, women, caste, and religious minorities. Smitha (2020) analyzed the NEP 2020 and their opportunities and challenges in teacher education. The main objectives of NEP 2020 is to “ensure that teachers are given the highest quality training in content, pedagogy, and practice by moving the teacher education system into multidisciplinary colleges and universities, and establishing the 4- year integrated B.ED offered by such multidisciplinary HEIs will, by 2030 become the minimal degree qualification for teachers. Sawant and Sankpal (2021) analysed the National education policy 2020 and states that With its ambitious and drastic changes, NEP (2020) has the potential to completely overhaul the county's educational system. It is going to bring about significant changes in India's educational system. Sharma (2021) described the National Education Policy in the terms of language perspective. Education policy is an important initiative towards ensuring the all- round development of Indian society. It aims to promote the preservation and development of all Indian languages. Verma and Kumar (2021) were of the view that new If the central government's National Education Policy 2020 is executed effectively, it could alter the Indian educational system to suit the demands of the twenty-first century India. Ranjan and Mohapatra (2023) states that the goal of a holistic and multidisciplinary education would be to combine the intellectual, artistic, social, physical, emotional, and moral development of all human capacities. Eventually, all undergraduate programs—including those in professional, technical, and vocational fields—will adopt an all-encompassing approach to teaching.

Though, there exists multiple studies regarding the NEP (2020), but scant attention seems to have been paid so far as the study on its implementation in the schools and colleges is concerned. Thus, this calls for the need to conduct a comprehensive study about its implementation, its pros and cons and the actual problems faced by the educational institutions in its effective implementation. Keeping this in mind, the present study has been proposed to conduct a detailed study about NEP (2020).

Data Base and Methodology

The present study was undertaken with following objectives:

1. To study the initiatives taken by Central Govt. for the implementation of NEP 2020 in school Education.
2. To study the initiatives taken by Central Govt. for the implementation of NEP 2020 in higher education.
3. To study the initiatives taken by Central Govt. for the implementation of NEP 2020 in Teacher Education.

In order to achieve these objectives, the primary data were collected from the various schools and colleges, using questionnaire method. Schools and colleges were selected by resorting to the method of convenience sampling.

Following Table shows the lists of schools and colleges from where the requisite data was collected.

S no.	Name of the Schools (Govt. and Non-Govt.)	No. of Teachers
1	Govt. Senior Secondary School (Wadali Guru)	10
2	Govt. Senior Secondary School (Goal Bagh)	10
3	Govt. of Eminence (Chheharta)	10
4	Govt. High School (Kala)	10
5	Govt. Senior Secondary School (Khasa)	10
6	Cambridge International School, Patti	10
7	Delhi Public School, Amritsar	10
8	M.KD D.A.V Public School (NESTHA)	10
9	DAV Public School, Amritsar	10
10	Bharti Vidhya Bhawan SL Public School	10

S no.	Name of the Colleges	No. of Teachers
1	DAV College, Amritsar	10
2	Hindu College, Amritsar	10
3	SSSS College of Commerce for Women, Amritsar	10
4	SR Govt. College, Amritsar	10
5	Ragunath college Jandiala guru , Amritsar	10
6	DAV College of Education for Women, Amritsar	10
7	S.G.T.B College of Education, Khankot	10
8	Anand College of Education, Amritsar	10
9	Khalsa College of Education, G.T Road, Amritsar	10
10	Khalsa College of Education, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar	10

Percentage Analysis was conducted on the data, thus, collected and the results were presented in the form of table and graphs.

Data Analysis

This section has been divided into three sub-sections. The *first sub-section* deals with school education analysis; the *second section* deals with college education and the *third section* deals with teacher education.

SECTION- I SCHOOL EDUCATION

Table 1: Responses of the Teachers in Government and Non-Government Schools

Parameter	Government schools		Non- schools	government
	YES	NO	YES	NO
Awareness of the policy passed in 1968 ,followed by 1968 and revised in 1992	48 (96%)	2 (4%)	50 (100%)	0 (0 %)
Awareness of the NEP 2020 policy	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Foundational stage as a part of formal school settings	25 (50%)	25 (50%)	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)
Teachers trained on the new pedagogical practices	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)
Facility of high quality infrastructure and play equipment for ECCE	20 (40 %)	30 (60 %)	40 (80 %)	10 (20 %)
Teachers pursuing 6 Months certificate programme in ECCE and 1 year diploma programme	10 (20 %)	40 (80 %)	40 (80 %)	10 (20 %)
Taking Students to field trips	30 (60 %)	20 (40 %)	40 (80 %)	10 (20 %)

Teachers utilising the national repository of high quality resources, available on DIKSHA	30 (60%)	20 (40%)	43 (86%)	7 (14%)
Children undergoing health check ups	30 (60%)	20 (40%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Health cards issued to the students	40 80%	10 20%	40 80%	10 20%
Basic Facilities hostel and conveyance provided to the students	13 (26%)	37 (74%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Record of the students attendance maintained by the school	50 (100%)	0 (0%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Provide facilitating system for equitable and quality education to the students	50 (100%)	0 (0%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Schools adopted both formal and non formal education	47 (94%)	3 (6%)	40 (80%)	10 (20%)
Schools offering Sanskrit as an optional subject	30 (60%)	20 (40%)	30 (60%)	20 (40%)
Changes in the assessment and Revaluation system introduced by NEP	40 (80%)	10 (20%)	33 (66%)	17 (34%)
Institution has proper Laboratory and Internet facilities.	33 (66%)	17 (34%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Staff attending 50 hrs CPD program	0 (0%)	50 (100%)	40 (80%)	10 (20%)
NEP 2020 will bring drastic change in the education system	50 (100%)	0 (0%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020	50 (100%)	0 (0%)	50 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 1 shows that in case of Government schools surveyed, 96 percent teachers had awareness about previous policies of NEP 1968, NEP 1986 and POA 1992, while 4 percent were not aware about previous policies. But all of the teachers had awareness about National Education Policy 2020. On the other hand, in non govt. schools, all the teachers had awareness about previous policies as well as NEP 2020. 50 percent teachers in the government schools agreed that foundational stage must be a part of their school settings, while in non-government schools, all the teachers were in the favour of foundational stage to be considered as a part of their school settings. Furthermore, in government schools as well as in non -government schools, all teachers have been trained on the new pedagogical practice. In government schools 40 percent teachers agreed that there is a facility of high quality infrastructure and play equipment for ECCE in their schools & 60 percent did not agree with this. In non -government

schools 80 percent agreed that there is a facility of high quality infrastructure and play equipment for ECCE in their schools and 20 percent teachers did not agree with this. So far as, 6 months program in ECCE is concerned, in government schools 20 percent have completed it and 80 percent did not complete it yet & In non- government schools 80 percent teachers have pursued it, while 20 percent have not pursued it. In government schools 60 percent teacher agreed that their schools provide facility of taking the students to field trips & 40 percent did not agree. 60 percent teachers are also utilising the DIKSHA App. In Non- government school 80 percent teachers agreed that their schools provide facility of taking students to field trips & 20 percent did not agree.

The NEP 2020 also recommends for a periodic health check -up of the overall system by conducting sample- based National Achievement Survey. In government schools 60 percent teachers were of the view that their school children are undergoing health check- ups especially for 100 percent immunization in school & In non- government schools 80 percent of the teachers gave opinion that the children have been issued health cards as well as 100 percent gave opinion about the health check -up done regularly. In government schools 26 percent of the teachers gave opinion about the hostel and conveyance facilities have been provided to the students while in non- government schools all the teachers agreed that there is a facility of hostel and conveyance in their schools. In government and non -government schools both, all teachers agreed that there is a proper maintenance of record of the students. Both government and non -government schools all teachers agreed that their institutions provide equitable and quality education to the students. In government schools 94 percent & in non -government schools 80 percent of the teachers were of the view that their institutions adopted both formal and non- formal education. In government schools and non- government schools both, 30 teachers agreed that schools offering Sanskrit as optional subject. 20 teachers did not agree with this. In government schools 80 percent of the teachers gave opinion about the changes in the assessment and revaluation system introduced by NEP 2020 in the schools while in non- government schools only 66 percent teachers have their same view.

According to NEP 2020 the use of technology can help improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the education system. Providing students with access to a wide range of resources and enabling them to learn at their own pace. In Government schools 33 teachers admit that their institutions have laboratory and internet facilities while in non- Government schools all the teachers admitted that their institution have internet and laboratory facilities. Both government and non -government, all teachers agreed that NEP 2020 will bring drastic

change in our education system & both the teachers of government and non -government schools satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020. As regards the different methods (Activity based, Inquiry based, play way based, Lecture based) for the implementation of foundational school settings) majority teachers of government and non -government schools, they were of the view that activity based and play based are the best for the classes of foundational stage because it makes the child more skilful and increases his/ her mental ability. Moreover, it encourages children to learn via hands- on, activities, exploration and games and also students can get knowledge easily involving themselves as playfully.

Majority of the teachers were in the favour of being bilingual in early childhood education. They were of the opinion that it makes the child a good learner and also it will help the students for their future life. It also enables the child to grasp things easily at early stage. While some of the teachers were not in the favour of the bilingual language, Students will not be so interested in learning different languages so the use of mother tongue should be promoted. All the teachers of the government and non- government schools, supported reduction in the syllabus to core essentials with experimental learning and critical thinking, as it will lessen the burden on students for gaining a higher percentage of marks and reduce mishaps such as suicides and depression due to stress of studies. Moreover, it indulges the students in extra-curricular activities.

As per the NEP 2020, the government is planning to regulate the fees of private institutions, about 70% teachers agreed that it is a right move to curb high fees, because it may attract students more towards private institutions from weaker sections of the society and there must be monthly strict check or audit by the government officials to implement the same in real. In private schools, fee structure is increasing day by day and most of the parents feel burden to pay such a large amount of fees. So government should make right and appropriate move to control the high fees.

Majority of the teachers were satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020 in school education, But the institutions are facing certain challenges to implement NEP 2020 like, 60% of government institutions reported inadequate technological infrastructure, outdated hardware and limited internet connectivity, insufficient digital resources etc.

SECTION II: HIGHER EDUCATION**Table 2: Responses of the Teachers in Colleges**

Parameter	YES	NO
Awareness of Previous policies NEP 1968, NEP 1986 and POA 1992	43 (86%)	7 (14%)
Awareness of changes in the higher Education system introduced by NEP 2020	50 (100%)	0 (0%)
Faculty members trained on the new pedagogical practices	30 (60%)	20 (40%)
Institutions implementing the new curricular and pedagogical changes.	25 (50%)	25 (50%)
Changes in the assessment and evaluation in your institution.	29 (58%)	21 (42%)
Satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020.	35 (70%)	15 (30%)
Positive impact of NEP 2020 in higher education.	38 (76%)	12 (24%)
Planning of government to regulate fees of private institutions.	32 (64%)	18 (36%)
Institution allowing students to opt two degrees simultaneously	10 (20%)	40 (80%)
Institution have an International student office hosting students from abroad	4 (8%)	46 (92%)
Institution providing imaginative and flexible curricular structure	11 (22%)	39 (78%)
College setting up National Scholarship Portal to track the progress of students	31 (62%)	19 (38%)

In Higher Education colleges, 50 teachers had been surveyed. 86% teachers had awareness about the previous policy of NEP 1968, NEP 1986 and POA 1992. 14% were not aware about the previous policies. But, all the teachers had awareness of changes in the higher education system introduced by NEP 2020. In Higher Education colleges, 60 percent of the faculty members have been trained on the new pedagogical practices while 40 percent were not. Moreover, In colleges, 58 percent admitted changes in the assesment and evaluation in their institution while 42 percent did not have any idea about it. NEP 2020 have made significant changes in the higher education. 70 percent of the college teachers have been satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020. It has been proposed in NEP 2020, fees will be regulated in private institution in order to attract more students from economically weaker

sections of the society. 64 percent of the teachers admitted that it is the right move to regulate the fees of private institutions while 36 percent did not comment on it. Furthermore, 20 percent revealed that their institution allow students to opt two degrees simultaneously. Institutes having international student office help students from foreign countries to have their queries related to admissions, fee structure etc. 8 percent colleges admitted that their institution has an international student office while 92 percent did not reveal anything. 22 percent teachers admitted that their institution have flexible curriculum structure.

With the active participation of the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, the National Scholarship Portal has been launched so that the students residing in different states and UTs will be able to get a single platform for getting details regarding the various scholarships launched for them. 62 percent of the teachers admitted that college have been set up National Scholarship portal to track the progress of students.

As regard the NEP 2020 in higher education, the Government have announced the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 provides that curriculum content will be reduced in each subject to its core essentials, to make space for critical thinking and more holistic, inquiry-based, discovery-based, discussion-based and analysis based. NEP 2020 policy offers flexible learning model which allow students to choose subject based on their interest. These promotes individualised learning and also help students to explore their passions and develop skills in their chosen field. Majority of the teachers agree with this statement that reduction in the syllabus to core essentials with experimental learning and critical thinking will lessen the burden on students for gaining a higher percentage of marks and reduce mishaps such as suicides and depression due to stress of studies.

According to National Education Policy 2020, the Universities and institute offering single streams will be phased out to multidisciplinary up to 2040. The teachers were of the opinion that it will affect the expertise of current people and job opportunities of all streams. 90 percent teachers agreed that their institution follow undergraduate degree with either 3 or 4 years duration. The teachers also gave opinion that their institution have been working on the development of cognitive skills and learning outcomes, Socio- economically disadvantages areas, Emphasis on Research, Merit-base career management and progression of faculty. Teachers were of the view that there are certain challenges, their institution is facing to implement NEP 2020, such as the need for substantial investment in education, the lack of adequate infrastructure and resources, the shortage of trained teachers, the challenge of providing quality education in remote and rural areas.

SECTION III: TEACHER EDUCATION**TABLE 3: Responses of Teachers in Colleges**

Parameter	YES	NO
Awareness of NEP 2020	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)
Awareness of the changes introduced by NEP 2020	40 (80%)	10 (20%)
Teacher educators in the institution trained on the new pedagogical practices	39 (78%)	11 (22%)
Institution implementing the new curricular and pedagogical changes recommended by NEP 2020	46 (92%)	4 (8%)
Government plan to regulate the fees of private institution	33 (66%)	17 (34%)
Changes brought by NEP in the assessment and evaluation of institution	43 (86%)	7 (14%)
Satisfactory changes brought by NEP 2020 in teacher education	40 (80%)	10 (20%)
Teacher education programmes having adequate availability of a range of experts in education	45 (90%)	5 (10%)
Institutions having a network of government and private schools to work closely with private teachers	46 (92%)	4 (8%)

The NEP 2020 enacts numerous changes in India's education policy. The NEP 2020 has addressed the issues and concerns of teachers and teacher education and made recommendations to ensure quality teachers at all levels of education. In teacher education, all the teachers out of 50 admitted that they have heard of NEP 2020, While 80 percent had awareness of the changes introduced by NEP 2020. Pedagogy refers to the way of teaching students, whether it is the theory or practice of education. It helps in improving the quality of education. 78 percent of the teachers are trained on the new pedagogical practices, while 92 percent of the teachers admitted that their institution implemented the new curricular and pedagogical changes recommended by NEP 2020. As per NEP 2020, all the fees and charges set by these institutions will be transparently and fully disclosed, and there shall be no arbitrary increase in the fees during the enrolment of each student. 66 percent of the teachers admitted that the government has regulated the fees of private institution while 86 percent accepted the changes brought by NEP 2020 in the assessment and evaluation of institution.

NEP 2020 recognizes the role of technology in enhancing the teaching learning process. It promotes the integration of technology in education through the establishment of digital infrastructure. 80 percent of the teachers admitted the satisfactory changes brought by NEP 2020 in teacher education.

In teacher education 90 percent of the teachers admitted that their institutions have adequate availability of range of experts in education while 92 percent revealed that institutions have a network of government and private schools to work closely with private teachers.

As regard the positive impact of NEP 2020 on teacher education, the teachers gave the opinion that new pedagogical and assessment practice, proving very beneficial for the institution. Through NEP 2020, the evaluation system has been getting better. Majority of the teachers were satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020 in teacher education. NEP 2020 envisages that outstanding faculty with demonstrated leadership and management skills will be identified and trained over time to take on important leadership positions.

Teachers were of the opinion that NEP 2020 increase the focus on strengthening teacher training, reforming the existing exam system, early childhood care and restructuring the regulatory framework of education. It was observed that all the teacher education institutions had a network of government and private schools to work closely with potential and they follow up to the technology platforms for online training of teachers inculcated into standardized training programmes.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS:

In School Education -As regards the different methods (Activity based, Inquiry based, Play way based, Lecture based) for the implementation of foundational school settings) majority teachers of government and non -government schools, they were of the view that activity based and play based are the best for the classes of foundational stage because it makes the child more skilful and increases his/ her mental ability. Majority of the teachers were in the favour of being bilingual in early childhood education. All the teachers of the government and non- government schools, supported reduction in the syllabus to core essentials with experimental learning and critical thinking, as it will lessen the burden on students for gaining a higher percentage of marks and reduce mishaps such as suicides and depression due to stress of studies. Majority of the teachers were satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020 in school education, But the institutions are facing certain challenges to implement NEP 2020 like, 60% of government institutions reported inadequate technological infrastructure, outdated hardware and limited internet connectivity, insufficient digital resources etc. The teachers agree

with this statement that reduction in the syllabus to core essentials with experimental learning and critical thinking will lessen the burden on students for gaining a higher percentage of marks and reduce mishaps such as suicides and depression due to stress of studies. Teachers were of the view that there are certain challenges, their institution is facing to implement NEP 2020, such as the need for substantial investment in education, the lack of adequate infrastructure and resources, the shortage of trained teachers, the challenge of providing quality education in remote and rural areas. As far as teacher education is concerned, teachers were of the opinion that NEP 2020 has positive impact on teacher education. The teachers were of the view that new pedagogical and assessment practice will prove very beneficial for the institution. Through NEP 2020, the evaluation system has been getting better. Majority of the teachers were satisfied with the changes brought by NEP 2020 in teacher education. NEP 2020 envisages that outstanding faculty with demonstrated leadership and management skills will be identified and trained over time to take on important leadership positions. Teachers were of the opinion that NEP 2020 increase the focus on strengthening teacher training, reforming the existing exam system, early childhood care and restructuring the regulatory framework of education. It was observed that all the teacher education institutions had a network of government and private schools to work closely with potential and they follow up to the technology platforms for online training of teachers inculcated into standardized training programmes. But there are certain challenges related to the implementation of NEP 2020. There may be lack of cooperation from States as education is part of concurrent list so State government can oppose the implementation of NEP 2020. Non- Availability of skilled teachers for elementary education may create hindrance in the effective implementation of NEP 2020. Proper steps have not been taken by administrative bodies to see whether schools are charging reasonable fees or not. The inclusion of more technology in learning environment may also be considered as a double edge sword. On one hand, it may enhance the learning experience for students in urban areas, but on other hand, it will put students and educators in rural areas at a disadvantage due to lack of experience with the technology. NEP 2020 may be opposed by some parents as early learning in local language but as a trend is of western culture. It will be challenge as local languages are ignored. In secondary stage many students of rural areas have no access to education so that they start doing agriculture work or any other work government should make necessary arrangement for imparting education in those area. Area of research is the most ignored area by government so it is suggested that to promote research, National Research Foundation should be set up. Various initiative for internship and vocational training of student should be

taken. For meeting the gross enrolment ratio standard Central and State government should work in coordinated manner for providing special packages to education institution. More university should be set up having holistic approach toward children development with sports culture research and development. Autonomous institution needs to be set up.

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